

INVERSE HEAT TRANSFER PROBLEMS IN COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Two inverse problems for the transient heat transfer inside composite media are discussed. The problems considered are the determination of the effective thermal conductivity and the estimation of the interface thermal contact conductance between the fibers and the matrix. The geometry is for the fibers arranged with the axes normal to the heated surface. The direct heat conduction problem is two-dimensional and is solved using a finite element program. An experiment for estimating the interface thermal contact conductance is suggested.

1. INTRODUCTION

There are many possible inverse problems associated with composite media. This paper is concerned with a class of inverse problems called parameter estimation [1] and is related to heat conduction. The same techniques, however, apply to other aspects such as processing of the materials and investigations of mechanical properties.

Han and Cosner [2] studied steady-state heat conduction in a class of fiber-matrix composite materials. The purpose of their study was to determine the steady-state effective thermal conductivity in the direction perpendicular to axes of the fibers. Thermal contact resistance between the fiber and matrix was neglected.

The problem considered herein is transient heat conduction in the fibers and surrounding matrix with the major heat flow in the direction of axes of the fibers. The fibers are packed as shown in Fig. 1a; the packing ratio considered is 64%. The basic element is the circular fiber surrounded by a hexagonal region which yields a three-dimensional problem; in order to reduce the complexity, the basic element is modeled as a composite cylinder as shown by Fig. 1b. The problem is still three-dimensional but only two coordinates are needed, r and z . It is expected that the idealization (Fig. 1b) would yield temperatures that are "close" to those found for the Fig. 1a geometry.

Fig. 1a

Fig. 1b

Figure 1. Fiber-matrix composite geometry.

For the fine fibers typically used (about 2 microns = $2E-6$ m in diameter), the surface area between the fibers and the matrix is large. As a consequence, the thermal resistance at the fiber-matrix interface can have larger effects for the small diameter fibers. The effect of the thermal contact resistance at the interface is examined in this paper.

In order to estimate parameters such as the thermal conductivity or the contact resistance, it is necessary to perform experiments and to obtain appropriate measurements. Due to the minute size of the fibers, it is not practical to attempt to measure local temperatures. It is practical to measure average surface temperatures, however, by using an extremely thin film of gold sputtered on the surfaces of a layer of composite material. The electrical resistances of the gold films would be calibrated as a function of temperature. A constant electric current would be suddenly applied at $z = 0$. The average temperatures at $z = 0$ and L would be measured during the experiment by using the known voltage versus temperature calibrations for the gold films. Very small real times have the greatest potential for estimating the parameters as discussed below.

There are several objectives in this paper. One is to show the average temperatures, $\bar{T}(z,t)$, for the fiber-matrix composite as a function of time for several thermal conductivity ratios, thermal contact resistances, and length to radius ratios, L/r_2 . Another objective is to demonstrate an estimation procedure for effective thermal conductivity. The third objective is to investigate the estimation of the thermal contact conductance from transient measurements.

The outline of the remainder of the paper is now given. Section 2 gives a mathematical statement of the physical problem. Section 3 discusses the numerical solution of the transient heat conduction problem. Section 4 presents an analysis and the results of the parameter estimation

problem of determining the effective thermal conductivity. Section 5 discusses the thermal contact conductance problem.

2. MATHEMATICAL DESCRIPTION

The describing differential equations for the regions $0 < r < r_1$ and $r_1 < r < r_2$ for $z > 0$ are given by

$$k_i \left[\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \frac{\partial T_i}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{\partial^2 T_i}{\partial z^2} \right] = \rho c \frac{\partial T_i}{\partial t} \quad (1)$$

where $i = 1$ is for the fiber, i.e., solid cylinder, and $i = 2$ is for the matrix, i.e., annulus from $r = r_1$ to r_2 . (See Fig. 1b.) The respective thermal conductivities are k_1 and k_2 but the density-specific product, ρc , is the same for both regions. The T denotes temperature and t denotes time.

The boundary condition at $z = 0$ is chosen to be the basic case of a constant heat flux, q_0 , and the boundaries at $z = L$ and $r = r_2$ are assumed to be insulated,

$$-k_i \left. \frac{\partial T_i}{\partial z} \right|_{z=0} = q_0, \quad \left. \frac{\partial T_i}{\partial z} \right|_{z=L} = 0, \quad \left. \frac{\partial T_2}{\partial r} \right|_{r=r_2} = 0 \quad (2a,b,c)$$

Moreover, at $r = 0$, there is also a symmetry condition and the initial temperature distribution is zero,

$$\left. \frac{\partial T_1}{\partial r} \right|_{r=0} = 0, \quad T_i(r, z, 0) = 0 \quad (3a,b)$$

At the interface, $r = r_1$, there is a thermal contact conductance, h_c , and hence the interface condition is

$$-k_1 \left. \frac{\partial T_1}{\partial r} \right|_{r_1^-} = h_c [T_1(r_1^-, z, t) - T_2(r_1^+, z, t)] = -k_2 \left. \frac{\partial T_2}{\partial r} \right|_{r_1^+} \quad (4)$$

Two sets of thermal conductivity ratios $k_1/k_2 = 10$ and $k_1/k_2 = 0.1$, two different h_c values, and two different L/r_2 ratios (10 and 20) are considered. A total of eight cases are considered and are listed in Table 1. For each case $r_1/r_2 = 0.8$ so that the fiber occupies 64% of the cross-sectional area.

The results can be conveniently plotted in the figures if the following dimensionless variables are introduced

$$T^+ = \frac{T k_i}{q_o r_2}, \quad t^+ = \alpha_i t / r_2^2, \quad B = \frac{h r_2}{k_i}, \quad L^+ = L / r_2 \quad (5)$$

where $i=1$ for cases 1, 2, 5 and 6 and $i=2$ for the other cases (3, 4, 7 and 8) and where $\alpha_i = k_i / \rho c$.

For the case of the conductivity ratio being unity, the temperature distribution becomes one-dimensional. For the case of h_c being equal to zero, there are two independent 1-D solutions, one for the fiber and one for the matrix. For these two cases the solutions can be given in a simple form. For one-dimensional heat flow and a constant heat flux, the heated surface temperature rise is [1, p. 454]

$$T(z, t) = \frac{q_o L}{k} \left[\frac{\alpha t}{L^2} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{z}{L} \right)^2 - \frac{z}{L} \right] \quad (6)$$

for dimensionless times, $\alpha = k / \rho c$, greater than 0.3.

In the estimation of thermal parameters such as the thermal conductivity or contact conductance, temperature measurements are needed. Due to the extremely small diameters of the fibers, local temperatures are not feasible to measure. However, average temperatures at the heated surface and at the insulated surface ($z = L$) can be measured by using a gold film as mentioned in connection with Fig. 1. The area-average temperature is

$$\bar{T}(z, t) = \frac{1}{\pi r_2^2} \left[\int_0^{r_1} T_1(r, z, t) 2\pi r dr + \int_{r_1}^{r_2} T_2(r, z, t) 2\pi r dr \right] \quad (7)$$

3. CALCULATED TEMPERATURES

The transient temperature distribution, $T(r, z, t)$, in the composite cylinder was calculated using TOPAZ [3] which is a finite element program. The average temperatures at $z = 0$ and $z = L$ were calculated using eq. (7) and are shown in Figure 2 for $L/r_2 = 20$ cases. Also shown are the temperatures for $k_1/k_2 = 1$, the one-dimensional case. A few comments are appropriate regarding the average temperatures shown in Figure 2. The difference between the dimensionless temperature \bar{T}^+ for any case and the $k_1/k_2 = 1$ case starts at zero at $t^+ = 0$ and increases to a maximum value. After a certain time period, each \bar{T}^+ increases linearly with time. The

same maximum dimensionless temperature difference is attained as L^+ and t^+ become large. This point is explored in the following analysis.

As the dimensionless time becomes large, the average surface temperature, $\bar{T}^+(0,t)$, calculated using eq. (7) can be related in a simple manner to an approximate (one-dimensional) surface temperature, $T_{\text{approx}}(0,t)$, where effective thermal properties are used. The dimensionless form of $T_{\text{approx}}(0,t)$ is found from eq. (6) as

$$\frac{T_{\text{approx}}(0,t)}{q_0 r_2 / k_{\text{eff}}} = \left[\frac{\alpha_{\text{eff}} t}{L^2} + \frac{1}{3} \right] \frac{L}{r_2} = \left[\left(\frac{r_2}{L} \right)^2 \frac{k_{\text{eff}}}{k_i} \frac{\alpha_i t}{r_2^2} + \frac{1}{3} \right] \frac{L}{r_2} \quad (8)$$

For a constant heat flux case, the difference between $\bar{T}(0,t)$ and the $T_{\text{approx}}(0,t)$ becomes a constant value for large times,

$$\frac{\bar{T}(0,t)}{q_0 r_2 / k_{\text{eff}}} = \left[\left(\frac{r_2}{L} \right)^2 \frac{k_{\text{eff}}}{k_i} t^+ + \frac{1}{3} \right] \frac{L}{r_2} + \Delta T^+(k_1/k_2, B) \quad (9)$$

where ΔT^+ is the correction added to the one-dimensional model to obtain the correct two-dimensional results. (Eq. (9) was verified using TOPAZ.)

An expression for the effective thermal conductivity can be derived by using the simple steady state model

$$k_{\text{eff}} A \frac{\Delta T}{L} = k_1 A_1 \frac{\Delta T}{L} + k_2 A_2 \frac{\Delta T}{L} \quad (10a)$$

where ΔT is the temperature difference from $z=0$ to $z=L$. Solving eq. (10a) for k_{eff} yields

$$\frac{k_{\text{eff}}}{k_i} = \left(\frac{r_1}{r_2} \right)^2 \frac{k_1}{k_i} + \frac{r_2^2 - r_1^2}{r_2^2} \frac{k_2}{k_i} \quad (10b)$$

Eq. (10b) is valid for both steady and quasi-steady state cases. The r_1/r_2 ratio in eq. (10b) is 0.8. For cases 1, 2, 5 and 6, $k_1/k_i = 1$ and $k_2/k_i = 0.1$ and thus $k_{\text{eff}}/k_i = 0.676$ and for the other cases, $k_{\text{eff}}/k_i = 0.424$. The expression for $\Delta T^+(k_1/k_2, B)$ is

$$\Delta T^+(k_1/k_2, B) = \bar{T}^+(0, t^+) \frac{k_{\text{eff}}}{k_i} - \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{L^+} \right)^2 \frac{k_{\text{eff}}}{k_i} t^+ + \frac{1}{3} \right\} L^+ \quad (11)$$

Values for $\Delta T^+(k_1/k_2, B)$ are given in the last column of Table 1. Notice that cases 1 and 5, 2 and 6, etc. show the effect of L^+ changing from 10

to 20. For cases 1 and 5, the ΔT^+ values are relatively close, about 2.18. The others are not as close but cases 5 to 8 are always smaller than the corresponding values for cases 1-4; this is because quasi-steady is not quite attained in the $L^+ = 20$ cases.

Figure 2. Average temperature at $z = 0$ (upper five curves) and $z = L$ (lower curves).

Table 1 Basic Cases Analyzed

Case	k_1/k_2	B	L^+	$\Delta T^+(k_1/k_2, B)$
1	10	0.01	10	2.180
2	10	0.10	10	0.584
3	.1	0.01	10	2.680
4	.1	0.10	10	0.881
5	10	0.01	20	2.160
6	10	0.10	20	0.457
7	.1	0.01	20	2.240
8	.1	0.10	20	0.391

$$B = h_c r_2 / k_j, \quad \begin{array}{l} j = 1 \text{ for cases 1, 2, 5 and 6.} \\ j = 2 \text{ for cases 3, 4, 7 and 8} \end{array}$$

One inverse problem that can now be formulated is the estimation of an effective thermal conductivity. Even though the problem is actually three-dimensional, the temperature distribution for physical times on the order of seconds (rather than milliseconds) is nearly one-dimensional.

To better appreciate the difference between physical time and dimensionless time, consider the case of thermal diffusivity being $1.0E-5 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ and r_2 radius of the matrix being $2E-6 \text{ m}$. Then for $\alpha t/r_2^2$ being equal to

1, the time t is $4.0E-5s$, a very small value. In order for the temperature distribution near the surface to come to a quasi-steady condition, a dimensionless time about $\alpha t/r_2^2 = 100$ (see Fig. 2) is required which corresponds to a physical time of $0.004s$, still a very small value. At this small time, there is a dimensionless temperature difference about 2 compared to a dimensionless temperature rise of about 10. For a constant heat flux at the surface of a semi-infinite body, the surface temperature continues to rise as $t^{1/2}$ while the temperature difference remains about 2, in dimensionless units of $\Delta T/(q_0 r_2/k)$. In order for this ΔT to be 1% of the temperature rise for a thermally semi-infinite body, the heating has to continue for much larger dimensionless times, about 40,000. This corresponds to a real time of 1.6s for this example. For times less than this, the average surface temperature would be significantly more than predicted using the effective thermal conductivity given by eq. (10).

4. ESTIMATION OF EFFECTIVE THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY

Presented in this section is the inverse problem of estimating an effective thermal conductivity from the average temperatures calculated in the two-dimensional analysis of Sections 2 and 3. The approximate model is the heat conduction equation,

$$k_{\text{eff}} \frac{\partial^2 \bar{T}}{\partial z^2} = \rho c \frac{\partial \bar{T}}{\partial t} \quad (12a)$$

subject to the boundary and initial conditions of

$$-k_{\text{eff}} \frac{\partial \bar{T}}{\partial z} \Big|_{z=0} = q_0, \quad \frac{\partial \bar{T}}{\partial z} \Big|_{z=L} = 0, \quad \bar{T}(z, 0) = 0 \quad (12, b, c, d)$$

where \bar{T} is the radial average temperature, eq. (7), and k_{eff} is the effective conductivity.

The procedure for estimating k_{eff} is discussed in [1]. The method of least squares is used. The "best" value of a parameter β (which is k_{eff}) is found by minimizing

$$S(\beta) = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^2 \left(y_{ji} - \bar{T}_{ji}(\beta) \right)^2 \quad (13)$$

with respect to β . The \bar{T}_{ji} values are found from a finite difference solution of eq. (12); the Crank-Nicolson method was used in the computer

program called PROPPC [1]. The index i refers to time t_i and the index j refers to positions $z_1 = 0$ and $z_2 = L$. The Y_{ji} are the corresponding values obtained from the 2-D calculation using TOPAZ.

The minimum of eq. (13) exists when,

$$\frac{\partial S}{\partial \beta} = \sum_i \sum_j \left[Y_{ji} - \bar{T}_{ji} \right] \left[-2 \frac{\partial \bar{T}_{ji}}{\partial \beta} \right] = 0 \quad (14)$$

Since \bar{T}_{ji} is a nonlinear function of β , one way to solve for $\hat{\beta}$ (the value which minimizes S) is to use the Taylor series for \bar{T}_{ji} ,

$$\bar{T}_{ji}^{(v+1)} = \bar{T}_{ji}^{(v)} + X_{ji}^{(v)} \left[\hat{\beta}^{(v+1)} - \hat{\beta}^{(v)} \right], \quad X_{ji} = \frac{\partial \bar{T}_{ji}}{\partial \beta} \quad (15a,b)$$

where X_{ji} is called the sensitivity coefficient. The v superscript in eq. (15) is an iterative index. Introducing eq. (15a) into eq. (14) and solving for $\hat{\beta}^{(v+1)}$ yields

$$\hat{\beta}^{(v+1)} = \hat{\beta}^{(v)} + \left[\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^2 \left[Y_{ji} - \bar{T}_{ji}^{(v)} \right] X_{ji}^{(v)} \right] / \Delta \quad (16a)$$

where

$$\Delta = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^2 \left[X_{ji}^{(v)} \right]^2 \quad (16b)$$

The iterations proceed until negligible changes occur in values of $\hat{\beta}$. (See also ref. 1.)

Note that n in eq. (16) is for all the "measured" times. After convergence of $\hat{\beta}$ is obtained, it is helpful to examine the effect upon $\hat{\beta}$ if the number of measurements were continually increased. This is called sequential estimation [1] which is a very important procedure and is now illustrated.

The $L^+ = 20$ cases are used (cases 5, 6, 7 and 8) in the estimation examples. The model is equation eq. (12). The results of the estimation procedure for the four cases are shown in Fig. 3. These results are for the converged values of k_{eff} using all the measurements from $t^+ = 5$ to 185 with steps of $\Delta t^+ = 5$. Consider the curve for case 5 which is for $k_1/k_2 = 10$ and $B = 0.01$. The estimated k_{eff} value is 0.44 when all the data is used. The other parts shown of the case 5 curve are also significant. For example, at $t^+ = 100$ the curve 5 value is 0.38; this value is the

Figure 3. Estimated effective thermal conductivity, k_{eff} , using the sequential method.

estimate of k_{eff} using the measurements only until time $t^+ = 100$. Since the k_{eff} values change with time, the one-dimensional model is not accurate for the time period considered. However, if the dimensionless time period were made much larger (and still correspond to a small real time), the one-dimensional model would predict nearly a time invariant k , which would be k_{eff} given by eq. (10b); such a one-dimensional model would be satisfactory for these very large dimensionless times.

5. ESTIMATION OF THERMAL CONTACT CONDUCTANCE

The estimation of the thermal contact conductance h_c can be obtained in the same manner as for the effective conductivity. The model now is eq. (1) with eqs. (2-4). The fiber and matrix thermal properties (k , ρ and c) are considered known. It is assumed that the average surface temperatures are measured in an experiment in which one surface is heated.

The concept is to minimize S given by eq. (13) with respect to the contact conductance h_c , which is the new β in eqs. (14,15). The effects of errors in Y_{ji} on the estimated values can be obtained by using eq. (16), which, in turn, requires values for the sensitivity coefficients.

The sensitivity coefficients for h_c for $L^+ = 20$ and $z = 0$ and $z = L$ are shown in Fig. 4. The $z = 0$ values start at zero and increase to a maximum positive value for sufficiently large times. The $z = L$ sensitivity coefficients are negative and are much smaller in absolute value than the corresponding values at $z = 0$.

The significance of the sensitivity coefficients on the accuracy of

Figure 4. Average sensitivity coefficient at $z = 0$ (upper four curves) and $z = L$ (lower curves).

the h_c estimates can be examined by using eq. (16) [1,4]. Consider the case of measurement errors in Y_{ji} being additive, having zero mean and constant variance σ^2 , and being uncorrelated. Then the variance of the converged $\hat{\beta}$ is approximated by [1, p.379]

$$V(\hat{\beta}) = \sigma^2 / \Delta \quad (17)$$

where Δ is defined by eq. (16b). The experiment should be designed to maximize Δ . (See [1], chapter 8). For the present experiment, maximizing the accuracy of the h_c estimates requires that the measurements of the temperature be made at $z = 0$. Also note that the sensitivity coefficients approach constant values, while the temperatures (Fig. 2) continue to rise. This indicates that the sensitivity coefficients are becoming smaller relative to the temperature rises in the body which suggests that the experiment be designed to have a short time duration. Estimates of h_c using program TOPAZ will be discussed in a future paper.

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